

**ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE
CLASSROOM OF THE ENGLISH IN TEACHING SPEAKING
USING INTERACTIVE METHODS**

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Abstract: According to this article, there are given one of the characteristic features of an interactive approach to learning is that the teacher does not give ready-made tasks, but encourages students to search for themselves. Compared with traditional learning, the interaction between a teacher and a student changes in an interactive way: the activity of the teacher gives way to the activity of the students, and the task of the teacher is to create the conditions for their initiative. The teacher refuses the role of a kind of filter, which passes educational information through itself, and acts as an assistant in the article, one of the sources of information. This teaches independence not only in educational activities, but also in life, which is actually important, in our opinion.

Key words: speaking, interactive games, interactive methods, “Five by five” method

The problem of enhancing students’ cognitive activity has always been one of the most relevant in the theory and practice of education. In search of ways to solve it, teachers mastered research and search methods, non-standard forms of conducting classes, didactic games, and the like.

Speaking as a type of speech activity primarily relies on language as a means of communication. The language provides communication between the communicators, because it is understood both by the one who informs the information, encoding it in the meanings of words selected for this purpose, and the one who receives this information, decoding it, that is, deciphering these meanings

and changing it on the basis of information your behavior¹. There are a lot of interactive teaching speaking methods and technologies for multilingual learners. Students really like this kind of work like Carousel, when two rings appear: internal and external. The inner ring is the students sitting motionless, and the pupils of the outer ring move clockwise or counterclockwise every 30 seconds. Thus, they manage to discuss several topics in a rather short period of time and convince the interlocutor that they are right². The organization of a workable, communicative group, especially in multilingual classes of education, is extremely important.

Before you organize small groups and The task of the preparatory stage, as a rule, is to

- determine the level of psychological readiness of students to learn using new educational technology;
- create conditions of psychological comfort and success for students.

The technology of learning in cooperation, being a technology of developmental learning, implies the “awakening and launching” needs for self-actualization, self-realization, self-improvement, that is, what we hope to develop in children. But this is difficult to do if the child has a low level of self-esteem, self-acceptance, an unmet need for love, understanding and acceptance from other people (teachers, classmates, etc.). Caring for a positive self-esteem of the child is one of the main concerns of a foreign school, in particular an American one, which has developed self-esteem & cooperation courses. By organizing interactive games

¹ Гурвич, П. Б. К вопросу о специфике методики преподавания иностранных языков как науки [Текст] / П. Б. Гурвич // Иностранные языки в школе. – 2013. № 4. – С. 3–9.

² Бим, И. Л. Методика обучения иностранным языкам как наука и проблемы школьного учебника [Текст] / И. Л. Бим. – М.: Просвещение, 1977. – 278 с.

with children, you can help children feel united with others, teach them to think clearly, research and analyze, make decisions independently and in a group, develop openness and courage to express their attitude to others, as well as help cope with their fears and stress. There are those qualities and aspects of character that will be necessary for them when working in a small group³.

The situation of success does not arise where the comparison of one child with another is allowed, the comparison of one group with another: personality development proceeds unevenly, discretely, and some children with such a comparison will always lose, lag behind, allegedly, the development of other children, which means will be deprived of a wonderful feeling of their strength and personal success. Success is the key to a positive attitude to study, to work, to yourself, an incentive to active work.

The organization of training in cooperation in multilingual classes requires special preliminary preparation taking into account the psychological features of the interaction of students in small groups. In this regard, the preparatory stage acquires great importance for students to understand the specifics of the teaching on the new technology, identify the motives for cooperation, the qualities of a partner, and create an atmosphere of psychological comfort for children. On the basis of the selected criteria for the formation of groups, the effectiveness of educational interaction is achieved in solving the problem.

After analyzing the textbook “Fly high“, we came to the conclusion that there are not enough exercises aimed at interaction. And since interactive forms of work imply interaction, which promotes the development of speaking skills and personal

³ Fu, Xiao. Motivational strategies in teaching English as foreign language [Text] / Xiao Fu // International journal of humanities and social science. – 2013. – Vol. 3. – P.

qualities such as initiative, communication skills and activity, we can offer the following development of abstracts of lessons using interactive forms⁴.

1. Learning more about London Purpose: repetition of the studied material, training of the studied vocabulary and the introduction of a new lexical material on the topic “Learning more about London”.

Form: “Five to Five”

Props: photos, pictures with the image of the sights of London.

Duration: 30 minutes.

During the classes

The teacher offers the class to share in 4 groups. Each group is given the text, it lacks a certain part. For example, in the first group – the fourth paragraph, in the second – the first, in the third – the second, in the fourth – the third. Students study the text and prepare for the fact that it will be necessary to present to the other group the part that is lacking. A representative is selected from each group, selects the basic information from the paragraph and goes to another group in order to present this material. Thus, the whole text is compiled, which is compared with the sample.

At the end of the lesson the results are summarized, the students discuss with the teacher what they have learned in the lesson.

The “Five by Five” method allows you to:

- at the same time to involve students in the whole group;
- familiarize with a sufficiently large amount of educational material for the lesson;
- develop students’ oral speech;
- differentiate tasks in accordance with the level of preparedness of students;
- develop the ability to work with the text.

⁴ Алхазышвили, А. А. Основы овладения устной речью [Текст] / А. А. Алхазышвили. – М.: Просвещение, 1988. – 124 с.

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